

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SOLUTIONS AND PERSPECTIVES ON ELECTRICAL ENERGY STORAGE IN ROMANIA'S POWER SYSTEM

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Abstract

Electrical energy storage is becoming a strategic element in Romania's transition toward an energy system based on renewable sources. This paper analyzes the current state of storage capacities, major ongoing projects, and prospects for expansion up to 2030. It presents large-scale battery solutions and pumped-storage hydropower systems, as well as the main challenges related to costs, infrastructure, and regulations. The results indicate significant yet insufficient progress compared to the estimated national demand. Accelerating investments and modernizing the legislative framework are essential for ensuring grid stability and Romania's energy security.

Keywords: electrical energy storage, large-capacity batteries, pumped-storage hydropower

1. Introduction

Electrical energy storage has become a central topic in the context of the transition toward renewable energy sources. In Romania, this issue is gaining increasing importance as the country aims to meet the climate-neutrality objectives established at the level of the European Union [1].

Romania benefits from a diversified energy mix, based on nuclear, hydropower, coal, natural gas, and renewable sources. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the installed capacities of wind and

photovoltaic energy; however, these sources are highly variable [2].

Such fluctuations create the need for energy storage to balance supply and demand, especially during periods when renewable generation exceeds consumption. Without efficient storage solutions, Romania risks facing challenges in maintaining the stability of the national electricity grid and in ensuring a constant energy supply to residential and industrial consumers [3].

Table 1

Electricity consumption, imports and exports 2024/2025

Indicator	2024	2025 (partial)	Source
Final electricity consumption (annual)	~50.5 TWh (2024)	First 7 months of 2025: ~29.37 TWh (slightly higher than 2024 for the same period)	INS Reports [4]
Net imports	Increased imports in 2024; in 2025 imports remain significant during periods of low domestic production	2024: record imports in certain months; 2025: high imports during months I–VII	INS Reports [4]
Exports	Lower in 2024 compared to 2023 (INS 2024 data)	2025: reduced during periods of internal deficit (provisional)	INS Reports [4]

According to data available by mid-2025, Romania had an installed battery storage capacity of approximately 240.7 MW and an energy storage capacity of around 404.9 MWh [5]. A World Bank report estimates that Romania could reach **4 GW** of battery storage capacity by **2030** and over **11 GW** by **2050** [6]. Analysis by Transelectrica indicates that, by 2030, the country will need between **2–4 GW** of power and **10–20 GWh** of stored energy to support the transition toward a system with a major share of renewables [7].

Given these data, it is evident that Romania has an urgent need for new electricity storage capacities within its national energy system. The pressure is increasing as aging coal-fired plants are gradually decommissioned [8] and replaced with renewable energy sources. Until recently, Romania relied almost exclusively on adjusting hydropower output during peak hours; however, periods of drought, heat, or low wind

have shown that in many scenarios [9], the system can no longer cope due to insufficient storage capacity. The Romanian Ministry of Energy has therefore declared energy storage a “zero-priority” within the national energy system, similar to initiatives in other European countries [10].

2. Energy Storage Solutions Applicable in Romania

In Romania, the main technological solutions for electrical energy storage are **large-capacity battery storage systems** and **pumped-storage hydropower (PSH)** facilities.

2.1 Large-Capacity Battery Storage

At present, battery energy storage in Romania is still in a developmental stage. At the beginning of 2024, there was only one installation integrated into the national energy system, with a capacity of **7 MW** [11]. In

addition, several establishment authorizations were issued by the **National Energy Regulatory Authority (ANRE)** for future projects associated with intermittent renewable generation plants. Major international players have also expressed interest in entering the Romanian storage market.

For instance, in **April 2024**, the company **Monsson** commissioned Romania's largest battery energy storage installation — **24 MWh (6 MW × 4 h)** — as part of a hybrid photovoltaic–wind–battery project

located within a wind farm in **Constanța**. This storage unit represents only the first stage of a broader project expected to reach a total capacity of **216 MWh**, using **locally manufactured batteries** produced by **Prime Batteries Technology**.

2.2 Battery Storage Projects

Several major battery energy storage projects are currently under development or construction in Romania.

Table 2

Battery Energy Storage Projects in Romania: Capacity (MW/MWh), Status, and Funding Source

Project / Developer	Installed Power (MW)	Capacity (MWh)	Status	Funding Source / Remarks
Nova Power & Gas Florești, Cluj	200	400	Under construction, expected operational by end of 2025	Private investment; expected to double national capacity
HELLENiQ Renewables Romania – Vaslui	186	186	Ready-to-Build (RTB)	Acquisition of a portfolio; storage component part of wind projects
Simtel / Energy Capital Group – Iaz, Caraș-Severin	≈98.6	~196	EPC contract signed (2025)	Partial PNRR grant (≥ RON 50 million) for battery system
Renovatio Trading Toplița, Harghita	≈30	60.96	Under development (completion by 2026)	PNRR grant eligibility ~RON 111.5 million; subcomponent I.4
Monsson / Prime Batteries Technology – Constanța (Mireasa Wind Park)	6 (Phase 1)	24 (Phase 1)	Operational (2024) – Phase 1 of 3	Hybrid wind–solar–battery project; domestic battery production
Electrica S.A. Group – Fântânele, Mureș	35	70 (tender launched)	Procurement stage (2025)	Storage system + 110 kV substation; PNRR scheme component

Furthermore, **Hidroelectrică** announced plans to install a **64 MW / 256 MWh** battery project at the **Iron Gates II (Porțile de Fier II)** hydropower plant, with an estimated investment of **€61.2 million**, as well as a **€16**

million investment in a **36 MW / 72 MWh** battery system at the **Crucea Nord** wind farm (108 MW).

2.3 Evolution of Installed Battery Storage Capacity in Romania (2025)

Table 3

Evolution of Installed Battery Storage Capacity in Romania – 2025

Date / Reference	Installed Power (MW)	Energy Capacity (MWh)	Remarks / Source
01.01.2025	137	269	Situation reported by Transelectrica at the beginning of 2025
01.04.2025	235	399	Data provided by Transelectrica
01.09.2025	249	434	Situation reported by Transelectrica
Estimated (end of 2025)	~400–500	~1,000–1,200	Estimate based on projects under development and public announcements – indicative value

2.4 Pumped-Storage Hydropower (PSH)

On the lower **Olt River**, there are several low-head hydropower plants equipped with reversible turbines; however, these have so far operated predominantly in turbine mode, not in pumping mode.

The **Lotru hydropower complex** is currently the **only facility in Romania equipped for both generation and pumping operation** (Figure 1). It is the most complex development on Romania's inland rivers, based on a design that concentrates flows and hydraulic

heads. The scheme collects waters from the **Lotru River basin** and neighboring basins, directing them gravitationally and by pumping toward **Vidra Lake**, which serves as the main reservoir [12].

The Lotru complex consists of the **Lotru–Ciunget Hydropower Plant (HPP)**, an underground facility with installed power of **510 MW**, $Q_{inst} = 80 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, and gross head = **809 m**, together with the **Petrimanu, Jidoia, and Lotru Aval** pumping stations.

Figure 1. Diagram of the Lotru Hydropower Complex – [12]

Several potential sites for the construction of **pumped-storage hydropower plants (PSH plants)** have also been identified (Figure 2, red dots).

Figure 2. Potential locations for pumped-storage hydropower plants – [12]

The main proposed projects include:

- **Tarnița–Lăpușești PSH** – Specification: 1,000 MW; reservoir capacity 14 million m³. Objectives: balancing the central and western grid areas; controlling power flow to/from Hungary.
- **Măcin–Turcoaia PSH** – Specification: 1,000 MW; lower reservoir – Danube River (no need for new lower reservoir works), upper reservoir 25 million m³, ideally located in a former stone quarry. Objectives: reducing renewable generation congestion in Dobrogea (wind + nuclear); managing energy exchange with Bulgaria and Azerbaijan.
- **Firiza Lake PSH and Izvorul Muntelui PSH** – Specifications: possible options of 500 MW or 1,000

MW (detailed analysis required). Objectives: controlling energy flow to/from Ukraine and Moldova.

- **Dubova–Poiana Mare PSH** – Specification: 750 MW; lower reservoir – Iron Gates I accumulation lake; upper reservoir – Sura Mare or Poiana Mare plateau; useful storage volume: 13 million m³. Objectives: regulating energy flows with Serbia, Hungary, and partially Bulgaria.

Such facilities could play a **significant role in balancing the national grid during periods of renewable surplus.**

According to Transelectrica data from the morning of September 29, 2025, almost **two-thirds of the installed storage capacity** was briefly used to **inject electricity into the grid.**

Total 5683 MW - Productia in 29-09-2025 ora 08:55:27

Figure 3. Electricity generation by source on the morning of 29.09.2025 [13]

As shown in Figure 3, at the morning consumption peak, about **2.8% of all electricity produced and injected into Romania's grid** came from storage installations — energy previously stored from the grid during low-price hours and released back during peak demand.

3. Projects and Initiatives in the Field of Energy Storage in Romania

Over the past three years, several **national programs and funding schemes** have been launched to stimulate investment in energy storage infrastructure.

3.1 National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) Funding

A key component of Romania's energy transition is represented by the **PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan)**, through which several sub-components target the development of storage capacities. Under **Component C.6 – Energy, Sub-component I.4 – Renewable energy sources and energy storage**, Romania allocated substantial non-reimbursable funds for the installation of **new electricity storage capacities** totaling approximately **240 MWh** by 2026.

The financing program launched in 2023 attracted over **80 project proposals**, with total capacities exceeding **1,000 MWh**, demonstrating a very high interest from private investors.

Notable beneficiaries of the PNRR funding include:

- **Simtel Team / Energy Capital Group** – construction of a **98.6 MW / 196 MWh** storage facility at *Iaz, Caraș-Severin County*, with eligible costs exceeding **RON 50 million**;
- **Renovatio Trading** – a project of **30 MW / 60.96 MWh** in *Toplița, Harghita County*, eligible for **RON 111.5 million** in grants;
- **Electrica S.A.** – a **35 MW / 70 MWh** storage project at *Fântânele, Mureș County*, including a 110 kV transformer substation.

The **Ministry of Energy** continues to support such initiatives, emphasizing that storage capacities are indispensable for the **integration of variable renewable generation** and for **enhancing grid flexibility**.

3.2 European and Private Initiatives

Romania is also participating in several European initiatives aimed at developing large-scale energy storage technologies. Through partnerships with entities such as the **European Investment Bank (EIB)** and the **World Bank**, feasibility studies have been launched for the potential construction of **pumped-storage hydro-power plants (PSH)** and **hybrid energy systems** combining renewable generation with battery storage.

In addition to public programs, **private sector involvement** has intensified significantly. Major domestic and international companies — including **Monsson, Prime Batteries Technology, Nova Power & Gas, Renovatio, Electrica, and Hidroelectrica** — are actively developing projects that will collectively increase the country's storage capacity to more than **1 GWh** by 2026.

4. Challenges in the Development of Energy Storage in Romania

Despite recent progress, Romania still faces a number of technical, economic, and regulatory obstacles that limit the large-scale adoption of storage systems.

4.1 Technical and Infrastructure Challenges

The main technical limitations concern:

- **Grid integration** – the lack of sufficient flexible substations and transmission lines for connecting large-scale battery systems;
- **Aging infrastructure** – much of the national grid requires modernization to accommodate bi-directional electricity flows;
- **Limited local production capacity** for batteries and related components, leading to dependence on imports and longer implementation times.

Furthermore, **hydrological variability** poses challenges for pumped-storage systems, as reduced water inflows in drought years may affect their efficiency.

4.2 Economic and Financial Constraints

Although the costs of lithium-ion batteries have decreased globally, they still represent a **significant investment burden** for developers. According to estimates from 2025, the **levelized cost of storage (LCOS)**

for large-scale batteries in Romania ranges between €120–150/MWh, depending on the technology used.

Additionally, **the absence of a mature market for ancillary services and capacity remuneration** makes it difficult for investors to recover costs solely through energy arbitrage. This situation highlights the need for new **regulatory mechanisms** that adequately reward storage services such as **frequency regulation, peak-load management, and balancing support**.

4.3 Legislative and Regulatory Barriers

The **legal framework** for energy storage in Romania is still evolving. Although ANRE has introduced a dedicated “**License for energy storage operation**”, many associated regulations — including taxation, grid connection, and market participation rules — remain ambiguous. Another challenge concerns **the classification of storage facilities** as both producers and consumers, which complicates tariff calculations and financial reporting.

In addition, the **long permitting and environmental approval procedures** can delay project development by more than 12–18 months, particularly for pumped-storage hydropower plants.

5. Perspectives and Future Directions

The medium- and long-term prospects for energy storage development in Romania are strongly positive. National and European projections indicate that **installed storage capacity will exceed 2–4 GW by 2030**, and could surpass **10 GW by 2050**, if current projects and policy measures are implemented as planned.

In the near term, the following directions are considered essential:

- **Accelerating the deployment of battery energy storage systems (BESS)** to accompany renewable generation projects;
- **Modernizing the transmission and distribution grid** to allow greater operational flexibility;
- **Implementing new remuneration schemes** for storage-related services in the balancing market;
- **Encouraging local production and R&D** in advanced battery technologies;
- **Resuming feasibility studies** and launching investments in large pumped-storage hydropower plants such as *Tarnița-Lăpuștești*.

In parallel, Romania must strengthen **regional interconnections** with neighboring countries to improve grid stability and facilitate energy exchanges in periods of surplus or deficit.

6. Conclusions

Electrical energy storage represents a **strategic pillar** of Romania’s energy transition and a **key requirement** for the stability and resilience of the national power system. Although current installed capacities are still modest —

roughly **400 MW / 1 GWh** by the end of 2025 — the pace of development is accelerating rapidly.

The combined use of **battery energy storage systems** and **pumped-storage hydropower** offers Romania a viable pathway to balance renewable generation variability, reduce dependence on electricity imports, and increase energy security.

To achieve the 2030 objectives, it is essential to maintain a consistent public-private partnership framework, ensure predictable financing mechanisms, and streamline the legislative process for energy storage projects.

In conclusion, **the expansion of storage capacities is not merely a technical option but a strategic necessity** for Romania’s sustainable energy future.

This work was carried out through the Core Program within the National Research Development and Innovation Plan 2022-2027, carried out with the support of MEC-ANC, project no. PN 23140103.

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